

Earthquake Resistant of G+3 building using STAAD.Pro

¹Priyanka Nagdeve, ²Rahul Balnath, ³Shrawani Kadu, ⁴Roshan Babar

Abstract— Earthquakes pose a significant threat to buildings, infrastructure, and human lives worldwide. Mitigating this threat requires rigorous engineering strategies, especially in regions prone to seismic activity. This abstract presents a comprehensive approach to enhance the earthquake resistance of a G+3 building project. The present study is done to design the structure considering earthquake forces and other forces i.e., dead load, live load and earthquake load and comparing the costing of a building. The building shapes to play an important role for making the structure earthquake resistant. This earthquake resistant structure is taken for the 3rd seismic zone and Nagpur region is taken for which the factor value is taken as 0.16. Approximately around 30% of India falls in the zone 3 of seismic region. The code used are IS 456:2000 and IS 13920:2016. Designs per IS 13920-2016 satisfy all provisions of IS 456-2000 and IS 13920-2016 for beams and columns. It is found that the steel quantity is more for IS 13920 as compared to IS 456. So ductile detailing is achieved using IS 13920.

Keywords— Earthquake resistant construction, Analysis, Design, IS456:2000, IS13290:2016.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the vulnerability of buildings to seismic events has garnered significant attention due to the devastating impact earthquakes can have on communities and infrastructure. As a result, engineering efforts have increasingly focused on developing strategies to enhance the earthquake resistance of structures particularly in regions prone to seismic activity. This introduction outlines the project's objectives and methodology for improving the seismic the seismic performance of a G+3 building utilizing

Manuscript Received May 5, 2024; Revised 15 May, 2024 and Published on May 30, 2024

Prof. Priyanka Nagdeve, Department of Civil Engineering, Suryodaya College Of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: priyanka.kalamkar1984@gmail.com

Rahul Balnath, Department of Civil Engineering, Suryodaya College Of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: rahulbalnath79@gmail.com

Shrawani Kadu, Department of Civil Engineering, Suryodaya College Of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: shrawanikadu2@gmail.com

Roshan Babar, Department of Civil Engineering, Suryodaya College Of Engineering & Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India. Mail Id: roshanbabar590@gmail.com

STAAD. Pro, a powerful structural analysis and design software.

The land shortages existing today due to population explosions always requires the construction of high-rise buildings. As the ground floor of multi-storey buildings grow, the building is exposed to external forces under the influence of earthquake and wind pressure, thus leading to structural instability and later structural failure. Therefore, to enable tall buildings to withstand lateral forces, an earthquake and wind analysis must be done and incorporated into the final construction of the building.

II. OBJECTIVES

- To model a G+3 building using BIM
- To do an earthquake resistance design of a G+3 building
- To compare the design using IS-456 and IS-13920
- To design G+3 building by IS 13920
- To design G+3 building by IS 456.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Earthquakes are the indication of transformation in the earth's internal structure. Seismic activity is common in most parts of the world, though the frequency of its occurrence is a function of local tectonic setup. The past earthquake experiences have demonstrated huge loss of life and building stock, affecting the social and economic conditions of a country. Though it is not possible to prevent an earthquake, the least that can be achieved in reducing the damage is to make the buildings earthquake resistant.

The researchers all over the world are attempting to produce cost-effective and efficient construction technology by making use of the locally available materials. For example, in Peru, researchers have made traditional adobe structures much stronger by reinforcing walls with plastic mesh. In India, engineers have successfully used bamboo to strengthen concrete. It was also found that even the non-engineered constructions sometimes possess the required resistance to earthquake ground motions. For example, the Assam-type traditional housing in North-eastern states and the Dhajji-Diwari buildings in Kashmir have good earthquake resistance.

Taking specific precautionary actions in accordance with recognized scientific recommendations can help to prevent or mitigate the effects of an earthquake. These precautions may help to reduce the loss of life and property in earthquake-

prone locations. It is imperative that the general public be educated on the need of following conventional precautions while building in situated earthquake locations. Various institute and workshops modification of engineering curriculum in light of regular earthquakes in various sections of the nation may be of tremendous assistance in minimizing damage.

Seismic waves shake the earth, inflicting homes to collapse, and disturb the transportation and disturb the supply chain of basic need like milk fruits and vegetables. landslides and tsunamis are cause of earthquake and in the result of harm the peoples and cause of flood. seismic waves majorly affect the tectonic plates and in result of a movement take place in plates and disturb the earth surface. seismic waves are more often than not limited to seismic zones, which might be more often than not related to sea floor, semi ridges, and mountainous regions.

A Critical Review” The turf of seismic activity Engineering has existed in our nation for over 35 years now. Indian Earthquake Engineers have made momentous hand-outs to the seismic safety of a number of important structures in the country. However, as the recent earthquakes have shown, the performance of normal structures during past Indian earthquakes has been less satisfactory. This is mainly due to the lack of awareness amongst most practicing engineers of the special provisions that need to be followed in earthquake resistant design and thereafter in construction.

The tasks of providing full seismic safety for the residents inhabiting the most earthquake prone regions are far from being solved. However in present time we have new regulations in place for construction that greatly contribute to earthquake disaster mitigation and are being in applied in accordance with world practice. In the regulations adopted for implementation in India the following factors have been found to be critically important in the design and construction of seismic resistant buildings.

Earthquakes may create various kinds of causalities like loss of life and damage of property depending upon its magnitude; causalities could range from small property damage to landslides and a long range of liquefaction. Secondary effects like fire; blockage on services such as water supply, electricity, and transportation; and communication disruption are even more disastrous. Man-made infrastructures are however the major contributor of casualties during earthquake devastations. These structures therefore should be carefully designed and constructed. It is very important to develop new technologies to minimize these losses.

The researchers in Peru, have made traditional adobe structures by reinforcing walls with plastic mesh and they are much stronger. There are many examples such as in India, the engineers have successfully used bamboo to strengthen concrete and In Indonesia, some homes now stand in bearings which are very easy to make fashioned from old tires filled with sand and stones. Also, it was found that even the no-

engineered constructions sometimes possess the required resistance to earthquake ground motions.

With the advent of advanced technology, public buildings such as high-rise buildings and long-distance bridges are designed to evolve, increasing their inclination to the outside world. Therefore, these structures are at risk of extreme vibrations under the influence of strong winds and earthquakes. To protect these public buildings from severe structural damage, the earthquake response of these structures is analyzed and the calculation of wind power and forces such as support and removal of members are calculated and included in the design of the building that resists vibration. The main purpose of this paper is to construct an earthquake-resistant structure by conducting seismic research of the structure in an equitable analysis and analysis and design of the structure using STAAD. Pro software.

Earthquakes signal a change in the earth's internal structure. Seismic activity is frequent in most places of the world. Though an earthquake cannot be avoided, the least that can be done to minimise damage is to make buildings earthquake resistant. In the event of an earthquake, seismic waves from the epicentre are propagated across the entire region. The effects of lateral loads like as earthquake loads, wind loads, and blast forces have been a major issue in recent years.

STAAD PRO has the capability to calculate the reinforcement needed for any concrete section. The program contains several parameters which are designed as per IS: 456(2000). Beams are designed for flexure, shear and torsion. For Shear Design two-legged stirrups are provided to take care of the balance shear forces acting on these sections. Analysis and design carried in STADD. Pro and post processing in STADD. Pro gives the load at various supports.

S.no	Parameters	Description
1.	Utility of Building	Residential Building
2.	Dimension	18 x 12 meter
3.	No. of Stories	G+3
4.	Height of Building	12 meter
5.	Size of Column	200 mm x 400 mm
6.	Floor to Floor Height	3 meter
7.	External wall thickness	230 mm
8.	Internal wall thickness	115 mm
9.	Slab Thickness	150 mm

Figure 1: Live Load distribution on model

Figure 2: Rendering view of Staad-Pro Model

DESIGN BY IS 456:2000

		STAAD PRO	MANUAL
BEAM	B1	3 nos 8mm ϕ @ 100 c/c	2 nos 10mm ϕ @ 310c/c
	B2	4nos 8mm ϕ @ 120 c/c	3 nos 10mm ϕ @ 310c/c
	B3	2 nos 8mm ϕ @ 150 c/c	1 nos 10mm ϕ @ 310c/c
COLUMN	C1	8 nos 8mm ϕ @ 130c/c	6 nos 10mm ϕ @ 300c/c
	C2	8 nos 8mm ϕ @ 150c/c	6 nos 10mm ϕ @ 300c/c
	C3	8 nos 8mm ϕ @ 180c/c	6 nos 10mm ϕ @ 300c/c

DESIGN BY IS 13920:2016

		STAAD PRO	MANUAL
BEAM	B1	6 nos 8mm ϕ @ 120c/c	3 nos 10mm ϕ @ 360c/c
	B2	6 nos 8mm ϕ @ 150c/c	4 nos 10mm ϕ @ 360c/c
	B3	6 nos 8mm ϕ @ 180c/c	2 nos 10mm ϕ @ 360c/c
COLUMN	C1	3 nos 6mm ϕ @ 150c/c	2nos 6mm ϕ @ 250c/c
	C2	4 nos 6mm ϕ @ 200c/c	3 nos 6mm ϕ @ 250c/c
	C3	3 nos 6mm ϕ @ 250c/c	1 nos 6mm ϕ @ 250c/c

CONCLUSION

1. After comparing the STAAD.Pro and manual results it is concluded that the validation of project is done.
2. It is found that the steel quantity is more for IS 13920 as compared to IS 456. So ductile detailing is achieved using IS 13920.
3. In conclusion, the earthquake analysis using STAAD.Pro provides valuable insights into the behaviour of G+3 building under seismic loading conditions.
4. The study conclude that, analysing multi-storey buildings with Staad pro reduces manual computations and consequently provides correct results in less time.

REFERENCES

- [1] Adapa, Narendra कुमार. (2017) ‘The Static Analysis & Design of Residential Building Using Staad-pro V8i’, International Journal of Advance Technology and Innovative research, Vol. 09, pp. 0529-0536.
- [2] Aman, Manjunath Nalwadgi, Vishal T, Gajendra, “Analysis and design of multistory building by using STAAD Pro”, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), Volume: 03, Issue: 06, e-ISSN: 2395 -0056, p-ISSN: 2395- 0072, June-2016.
- [3] Babu Giresh B, “Seismic Analysis and Design of G+7 Residential Building using Staad-pro”, International Journal of Advance Research, Ideas and Innovation in Technology, Vol 3, Issue 3, pp 924-930, 2017.
- [4] Bhosle A.D, Hatkambkar Archit Pradip, Katkar Rupesh, Babar Shubham, Gorivale Sunny, “Analysis and Design Of Multi-storey Building by using Staad-Pro V 8i”, International Journal Of Innovative Science and Research Technology, Vol 3, Issue 4, pp-148-150, 2018.
- [5] Das Amresh. A, Bhaskar G.B, “Static and Dynamic analysis of Multistory Building”, International Journal of Research Trends and Innovation, Vol2, Issue 7, pp 192-198, 2017
- [6] IS 1893 (Part 1):2002, “Criteria for Earthquake Resistant design of structures”, Bureau of Indian Standards, pp 5-11.
- [7] IS 456-2000 code, “Plain and Reinforced Concrete”, Bureau of Indian Standards, pp 16- 32.
- [8] IS 875 (part1), “Code of practice for dead loads for buildings and structures”, Bureau of Indian Standards, pp 3-9.
- [9] IS 875 (part2), “Code of practice for live loads for buildings and structures for live load”, Bureau of Indian Standards, pp 5-7.
- [10] Kumar. Pavan, Naresh. A, Nagajyoti. M, Rajasekhar. M, “Earthquake Study of Multi Storied Residential Building” International journal of Engineering research and Applications Vol 4, issue 11, pp. 59-64, 2014.
- [11] Malarande, S.G, Agrawal, V., Dhawale, G.D., Dehane, A.B. and Nikhar, M.R. (2019), ‘Analysis and Design of Multi Storied Building Using Staad Pro and Manually for Two Seismic Zones’ IRE Journals Vol.3 , pp 13-15.
- [12] Pabba Mounika, Maraju Navya, Syed Viqar Malik, “Design of Residential building and Analysis withStaad-pro”, International Journal of Science Research and Development, Vol 3, Issue 11, pp 33-39, 2016.
- [13] Pathan. Irfan Khan, Dhamge. N.R, “Review Paper on Seismic Analysis of Multistoried RCC Building Due To Mass Irregularity” International Journal of Scientific Development and Research, Vol 1, Issue 6, pp 428-431, 2016
- [14] Patil, A.P., Choudhari, A.A, Mudhole, P.A., Patole, V.V and Dange, A.D. (2017), ‘Design and analysis of multistory building by using Staad- pro V8i’ International Journal of Advance Engineering, Management and Science (IJAEMS) Vol.3 , pp 277- 280.
- [15] Rani, Babitha., Babu, Nagendra., (2019), ‘Analysis and design of G+4 building using Staad-pro’ IJIRT Vol.4, pp 210-219